

Synthesis, Cytotoxic Activity (MTT, Caspase 8,9) Assay and Molecular Docking of Four New Hybrids (Curcumin –Ether Linker- 1,3,4- Oxadiazole) Compounds as Possible Anti-Cancer

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Abstract: Four novel hybrids (curcumin – 1,3,4- Oxadiazole) compounds ,namely 1,7 – bis [3-methyloxy ,4-(5-aryl -1,3,4- Oxadiazole -2- methyloxy -1- yl) phenyl] hepta 1,6- 3,5 dione [H7,-H10] were synthesized and the structures of all the synthesized compounds were characterized using (FT-IR , ¹H-NMR and Mass spectroscopy) and analysis of the spectral data obtained improve the final structure of compounds synthesized , and also these spectral data indicated the successful combination of curcumin and 1,3,4 Oxadiazole through ether linkage.Curcumin and hybrid curcumin [H8] compounds were tested for in vitro cytotoxic activities against one human cancer cell line named (SK-OV-3)as well as a normal cell line(HdFn).(MTT, Caspases 8,9) assays which are used to measure cellular metabolic activity, Cytotoxicity test result , showed that curcumin and compound[H8] has concentration dependent anti proliferative effect on SK-OV-3 cell IC₅₀ for curcumin = 149.4µg/ml IC₅₀ for [H8] = 81.30µg/ml, Curcumin and [H8] compounds are significantly reduced the viability of SK-OV-3 cell , the percentage of dead of early apoptotic and late apoptotic cell were detected to be Curcumin (21%, 61%) at 400 µg/ml on HdFn , SK-OV-3 cell. (16% (49% at 200 µg/ml on HdFn , SK-OV-3 cell respectively[H8] (27%, 69%) at 400 µg/ml on HdFn , SK-OV-3 cell respectively at 200 µg/ml on HdFn , SK-OV-3 cell respectively (61%,15%).

The Molecular docking study was conducted to determine the binding interaction of 1,3,4-oxadiazole , curcumin and the hybrid (curcumin -1,3,4- oxadiazole)compounds with two anti – apoptotic proteins ,namely β-cell lymphoma (BCL-2) and β-cell lymphoma – extra-large (BCL-x1).

The binding affinity , the presence of H- bonds between synthesized compounds and target proteins were also explained ,and the result obtained showed that compounds [H8] has the highest binding affinities of (-9.2 and -11.3)Kcal/mol , with (BCL-2 and BCL-x1) proteins The combination of the docking studies and cytotoxic evaluation of curcumin and [H8] showed that these compounds lower SK-OV-3 cell viability , increases pro apoptotic proteins, and decreases BCL-2 and BCL-X1 level therapy inhibiting SK-OV-3 tumor growth , these finding encourage us to development of anew synthetic strategy for cancer treatment.

The final result indicted that compound [H8] was potential as an anti-ovarian cancer and we need further studied for investigating its mechanism effect and in (vivo) preclinical studies using an animal model.

1. Introduction

Ovarian cancer is a common gynecologic malignancy, is often diagnosed as advanced stages and eventually dies of progressive, chemotherapy-resistant disease⁽¹⁾. Nearly all benign and malignant ovarian tumors originate from one of three cell types: epithelial cells, stromal cells, and germ cells. More than 90% of malignant ovarian tumors are epithelial in origin, 5%–6% of tumors constitute sex cord-stromal tumors and 2%–3% are germ cell tumors⁽²⁾. According to reports by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Global Cancer Observatory (GCO), ovarian cancer is one of the types of cancer that affects women in Iraq.⁽³⁾

Curcumin is the main active compound found in the turmeric plant (*Curcuma longa*) and is known for its multiple biological activities⁽⁴⁾. Curcumin is a polyphenolic compound known for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer effects⁽⁵⁾. There are several studies indicating that curcumin can inhibit the growth of cancer cells by interacting with multiple pathways in the cell⁽⁶⁾. It is thought to help prevent the spread of cancer cells and stimulate programmed cell death (apoptosis) in various types of cancer.⁽⁷⁻⁹⁾

Curcumin Hybrids are chemical compounds that are designed by combining curcumin with other molecules or chemical groups with the aim of improving its biological effectiveness or pharmacological properties⁽¹⁰⁻¹¹⁾. This approach aims to overcome some of the limitations of pure curcumin, such as low bioavailability and difficulty in absorption.⁽¹²⁻¹⁵⁾

1,3,4-Oxadiazole is an organic compound consisting of a pentagonal ring containing two nitrogen atoms and one oxygen atom⁽¹⁶⁾. This compound and its counterparts have broad biological activity, which is of great interest in the field of medicinal chemistry. Several 1,3,4-Oxadiazole derivatives have been studied for their potential to inhibit the growth of cancer cells, and have shown promising results in this context.⁽¹⁷⁻²⁴⁾

Molecular docking is a structure-based drug design approach that predicts the binding mechanism and affinity between receptors and ligands by simulating molecular interactions⁽²⁵⁾. Using the compounds database to screen possible pharmacophores not only makes it easier for researchers to acquire, synthesize, and conduct follow-up pharmacological testing, but it also increases efficiency and lowers research costs. Furthermore, the introduction of reverse molecular docking technology has the potential to considerably increase drug target prediction ability and understanding of the relevant molecular process for drug design⁽²⁶⁻²⁷⁾.

According to those observation which are prompted us to synthesized some new (curcumin - 1,3,4 – Oxadiazole) prodrugs, characterization of the above compounds using available spectroscopic instrumentation such as (FT-IR spectroscopy, H-NMR spectroscopy) and Mass spectroscopy. Molecular docking studies of a series of 1,3,4- Oxadiazole compounds and their linkage with curcumin. (curcumin – 1,3,4- Oxadiazole) prodrug were investigated as anti-cancer activity.

And we hope that the incorporation of 1,3,4- oxadiazole with curcumin may enhanced the biological activity of such compounds.

2. Materials and Methods

All chemical compounds acquired and obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, Merck, Aladdin, and Alfa aesar. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was used to monitor the course of reactions on silica gel pre-coated metal sheets. The melting points were measured using an uncorrected Stuart SMP10. FT-IR spectra (KBr disc) were measured at the University of Baghdad /Iraq- College of Science utilizing a SHIMADZU, Co., Germany spectrometer (4000-600 cm^{-1}). Spectra of Mass and ¹H-NMR for compounds generated in the labs of Sanati Sharif University/Tehran/Iran were recorded in DMSO-d₆ using a Bruker Ultershield 500MHz NMR spectrometer, Co., Germany.

2.1 Synthetic procedures: To synthesize intermediates and end products, the following procedures were performed, as illustrated in Scheme 1.

Scheme (1) : synthetic pathway of (curcumin – ether- 1,3,4- Oxadiazole) compounds [H7-H10]

2.1 A Synthesis of Chloro acetic acid hydrazone [H2] : Compound [H1], ethyl chloro acetate (0.01 mol, 1.22 gm) was added to hydrazine hydrate (80%) (5 ml), stirred for an 2 hours, Yellow faint precipitate was filtered, washed with cold ethanol, dried then crystallized from hot ethanol, m.p.(60-61 C°), (yield 78%).

2.1 B Synthesis of 2- Chloro methyl -5- aryl -1,3,4- Oxadiazoles [H3-H6] :

A mixture of Chloro acetic acid hydrazone (0.01 mol, 1.085 gm) and a appropriate aromatic acid (0.01 mol) and phosphorous oxychloride POCl₃ (5 ml) was refluxed (6 hrs), the cold reaction mixture was poured into (ice – water) and made basic by adding sodium hydroxide solution. the resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallized from chloroform.

Ar = -Ph [H3], 4-CH₃O-C₆H₄[H4],
4-Cl-C₆H₄ [H5], 3,5-diNO₂-C₆H₃[H6]

Table(1): Physical properties and yield% of 1,3,4- oxadiazole derivatives [H3-H6]

Comp. Sym.	Molecular formula	Molecular wt.(g/mol)	Description	M.P. (°C)	% yield
[H3]	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ Cl	196	brown powder	119–121	69
[H4]	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	225	White powder	250–251	77
[H5]	C ₉ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂	229	Brown powder	244–245	82
[H6]	C ₉ H ₅ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	285	Orange powder	196–198	86

2.1 C General Procedure for the synthesis of 1,7- bis- [3- methoxy ,4-(5-aryl – 1,3,4- Oxadiazol-2-methoxy-1-yl)phenyl]hept-1,6-diene-3,5-dione.[H7-H10]:

A mixture of one equivalent of curcumin , two equivalent of appropriate 1,3,4-Oxadiazole[H3-H6] and two equivalent of NaOH in appropriate amount of ethanol as solvent (25ml) was refluxed (24hr) . the reaction course was followed by TLC plate . the mixture was poured in acidic ice water (HCl) , the precipitate was filtered , washed with cold distilled water, dried , and the desired product recrystallizes from absolute ethanol .

The physical properties of the hybrid (curcumin – ether – 1,3,4- Oxadiazole) compounds [H7-H10]are listed in Table(2)

Table(2): Physical properties and yield% of hybrid (curcumin – ether – 1,3,4- Oxadiazole) compounds [H7-H10]

Ar= -Ph[H7],4-CH₃-O-C₆H₄[H8]

4-Cl-C₆H₄[H9],3,5-diNO₂-C₆H₃[H10]

Comp. Sym.	Molecular formula	Molecular wt.	Description	M.P. (°C)	% yield
[H7]	C ₃₉ H ₃₁ N ₄ O ₈	684.1	brown powder	252-255	78
[H8]	C ₄₁ H ₃₅ N ₄ O ₁₀	744.1	Yellow powder	250-251	77
[H9]	C ₃₉ H ₂₉ N ₄ O ₈ Cl ₂	753.1	Brown powder	220-229	82
[H10]	C ₃₉ H ₂₇ N ₈ O ₁₆	864.1	Orange powder	196-198	86

2.2 Biological activity :

Materials and methods

(Curcumin),[H8], doxorubicin , acridine orange , ethidium bromide and all materials used in tissue culture experiments were obtained from Sigma- Aldrich. The 3(4,5-dimethylthiazole-2-yl)-2,5 diphenyltrazolium bromid (MTT) kit was obtained from Intron Biotech(Korea). DNA reagent CycleTEST™ PLUS kit was obtained from BD Biosciences (USA) , while Caspase-9and 8 were obtained from Promega (USA). Multiparametric Cellomics cytotoxicity 3 kitand Cellomics oxidative stress kit were obtained from thermo Fisher Scientific (USA). Dimethyl sulfoxide was used to dissolve (Curcumin),[H8], at a concentration of 10 mg mL⁻¹ and stored at 4 °C until used . DMSO was used as a positive control with a final concentration of culture experiments . Reagents used in this study were of analytical grade , and solutions were prepared using highly purified water.

2.3 Molecular docking :

- Preparation of proteins : Crystal structures of the Bcl-2 and Bcl-xl proteins with PDB IDs 4IEH and 3ZK6, respectively, were obtained from the Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics (RCSB) Protein Data Bank. The crystal water molecules, ligand atoms, and ions that were bound to the proteins were removed. Hydrogen atoms were subsequently added using ADT.
- The ligands were drawn in Chem Draw Professional 16.0 and imported to Chem3D 16.0 to minimize energy using MM2 and saved as a sdf file extension in docking folder.
- The sdf file of ligand was converted into a pdb file extension via the Discovery Studio 2021 Client program.
- Making docking folder.
- The ligand pdb file was converted into a pdbqt extension by using Auto DockTools-1.5.6 programs and saved in docking folder.
- The protein was prepared by using AutoDockTools-1.5.6 programs as follows:

- n) Water molecules were removed
- o) Polar hydrogens were added.
- p) Kollman charge was added.
- q) The protein was saved as pdbqt file in docking folder.
- r) The docking process was performed by command prompt.
 - All molecular modeling calculations and docking studies were carried out via using linux program.
 - Making best conformation folder.
 - Discovery Studio 2020 Client software was used to explain the Grid Box, visualizing of ligand interactions, distances, 2D and 3D docking models.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Part one organic synthesis and characterization :

3.1 A Chemistry:

Chloro acetic acid hydrazide [H2] was obtained through the reaction of chloro ethyl acetate with excess hydrazine hydrate in ethanol solvent ,2-chloromethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole 2-aryl[H3-H6]were synthesized by rout in which chloroacetic acid hydrazide [H2] was condensed with appropriate aromatic acids in the presence of phosphorous oxy chloride which act as chlorinated agent and cyclo dehydrating agent , four novel hybrids conjucate named [H7-H10] were synthesized through the etherification reaction using Williamson method by the reaction of curcumin with two equivalent of 1,3,4-oxadiazole compounds [H3-H6] using NaOH as a base and ethanol as solvent.

3.1 B Characterization :

The (FT-IR) spectra of hybrids (curcumin-ether linker-1,3,4-Oxadiazole) showed bands for all the functional groups of curcumin and 1.3.4-Oxadiazole , for all the FT-IR spectra of [H7-H10] showed the disappearance of the O-H stretching vibration at 3520cm^{-1} of phenolic group of curcumin due etherification reaction, this disappearance give good indication for occurring this combination reaction .

Table (3) show the all spectral data (cm^{-1})of the functional groups presence in the Hybrid compounds .

Comp. symbol	C-H arom.	C-H aliph.	C=C Ring	C=N Oxadiazole ring	C-O-C (assym.)	C=O curcumin	others
H7	3012	2968(Asym) 2841(sym)	1581- 1448	1625	1209	1629	-
H8	3087	2958(Asym) 2921(sym)	1604- 1479	1631	1272	1628	-
H9	3053	2970(Asym) 2943(sym)	1595- 1456	1627	1280	1629	C-Cl: 958
H10	3016	2968(Asym) 2844(sym)	1575- 1456	1625	1209	1628	NO ₂ :1512(Asym) NO ₂ :1344(sym)

The ¹H-NMR spectra of hybrid (curcumin – ether linker- 1,3,4-oxadiazole) [H7-H10] showed the following features :

- All spectra showed signals at 2.5 and 3.3 ppm due to the protons of solvent (DMSO-d₆) .
- The curcumin moiety is characterized by three groups of signals :-

A- the methoxy group protons resonance appearing with in the (3.84 - 4.12) ppm.

B- Different peaks belonging to the olefinic and the phenyl protons appearing with the rang (6.89-8.88) ppm.

C- All the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of these hybrid molecules showed the disappearance phenolic proton at 9.90 ppm due to their resemblance to the ether linkage , disappearance of this signal give us a good indication of successful combination of curcumin with -1,3,4-Oxadiazole through ether linkage .

D- All the spectra [H7-H10] showed additional signal for $-\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$ - ether linkage at (5.46-5.79) ppm.

Table (4) give the exact value of (ppm) given to the different protons of hybrid(curcumin-ether-1,3,4- Oxadiazol) compounds (H7-H10) and figure (2)-(5) shows the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of these compounds .

Table (4): $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectral data of curcumin-ether linked- 1,3,4- Oxadiazol (H7-H10) ppm

Comp. Symb.	Chemical Shift(ppm)	No. of Protons	Type of single	Group
H7	3.84	6	s	(-OCH ₃ -)
	4.58	2	s	-CH ₂ -
	5.46	4	s	-OCH ₂
	6.92-6.89	2	d	CH=CH-
	7.75-7.74	2	d	CH=CH-
	8.04-6.97	16	m	Aro. Protons
H8	3.88	12	s	(-OCH ₃ -)
	4.62	2	s	-CH ₂ -
	5.49	4	s	-OCH ₂
	6.80-6.77	2	d	CH=CH-
	7.68-7.64	2	d	CH=CH-
	6.86-7.95	14	m	Aro. Protons
H9	3.91	6	s	(-OCH ₃ -)
	4.64	2	s	-CH ₂ -
	5.52	4	s	-OCH ₂
	6.93-6.97	2	d	CH=CH-
	7.63-7.66	2	d	CH=CH-
	7.01-8.88	12	m	Aro. Protons
H10	4.12	6	s	(-OCH ₃ -)
	4.78	2	s	-CH ₂ -
	5.79	4	s	-OCH ₂
	6.94-6.97	2	d	CH=CH-
	7.63-7.66	2	d	CH=CH-
	7.04-7.95	14	m	Aro. Protons

Figure (2): ¹H-NMR spectrum of (H7) compound

Figure (3): ¹H-NMR spectrum of [H8] compound

Figure (4): ¹H-NMR spectrum of [H9] compound

Figure (5): ¹H-NMR spectrum of [H10] compound

Finally, mass spectroscopy techniques was also used to characterized hybrid compounds [H7-H10].

- The Mass spectrum of compound [H7] showed an intense molecular peak at (684.1m/z) , corresponding to its molecular formula (C₃₉H₃₁N₄O₈) . Fragmentation pattern of this compound was confirmed by mass spectroscopy and the result shows highest peak at m/z (base peak) value (91.1) which indicting the most stable fragment ion , Mass spectrum of compound [H8] showed an intense molecular peak at (744.1m/z) , corresponding to it molecular formula (C₄₁H₃₅O₁₀N₄) . Fragmentation pattern of this compound was confirmed by mass spectroscopy and the result shows highest peak at m/z value (90.1) which indicting the most stable fragment ion , The Mass spectrum of compound [H9] showed an intense molecular peak at (753.1m/z), corresponding to it molecular formula (C₃₉H₂₉N₄O₈Cl₂) . Fragmentation pattern of this compound was confirmed by mass spectroscopy and the result shows highest peak at m/z value (91.1) which indicting the most stable fragment ion, and The Mass spectrum of compound [H10] showed an intense molecular peak at (864.1m/z) , corresponding to it molecular formula (C₃₉H₂₇N₈O₁₆) . Fragmentation pattern of this compound was confirmed by mass spectroscopy and the result shows highest peak at m/z value (90.1) which indicting the most stable fragment ion. There fragments were consistent with the fragmentation pattern of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole and curcumin Table (5) figure (6)-(9)

Table 5:Mass spectral data of curcumin-ether linked- 1,3,4- Oxadiazol (H7-H10) m/z

Comp. Symb.	Base Peak (m/z)	Other fragment (m/z)		
[H7] (C ₃₉ H ₃₁ N ₄ O ₈) 684.1m/z	91.1	647.1	524.1	500.1
[H8] (C ₄₁ H ₃₅ N ₄ O ₁₀) 744.1m/z	90.1	715.1	678.1	540.1
[H9] (C ₃₉ H ₂₉ N ₄ O ₈ Cl ₂) 753.1m/z	91.1	656.1	588.1	561.1
[H10] (C ₃₉ H ₂₇ N ₈ O ₁₆) 864.1m/z	90.1	820.1	737.1	712.1

Figure(6): Mass spectrum of [H6] compound

Figure(7): Mass spectrum of [H8] compound

Figure(8): Mass spectrum of [H9] compound

Figure(9): Mass spectrum of [H10] compound

the integration of the results obtained from (FT-IR , ¹H-NMR, Mass) spectral data gave a very good indication for the structures given to these hybrid compounds and also given a good indication for the successful of etherification reactions.

3.2 Biological activity

3.2 A Cytotoxic effect of curcumin on Ovarian cancer and healthy cell lines (MTT assay):

The invitation of Cytotoxicity of (curcumin), [H8], was done by MTT assay (This colorimetric assay is based on the reduction of a yellow tetrazolium salt (3-(4,5- dimethylthiazol -2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazoliumbromide or MTT) to purple formazan crystals by metabolically active cells. The viable cells contain NAD(P)H – dependent oxidoreductase enzymes which reduce the MTT to formazan . The insoluble formazan crystals are dissolved using a solubilization solution and the resulting colored solution is quantified by measuring absorbance at(570nm) using a multi-well spectrophotometer ⁽²⁸⁾. (The darker the solution , the greater the number of viable , metabolically active cell).

The cytotoxic impact of curcumin, against tumor cell line: **SK-OV-3** in addition to normal; cell line HdFn was assessed using the MTT test. This assay was performed using a range of concentrations (400 ,200, 100, 50 and 25 µg/ml) to detect cell viability. Results show that all compounds inhibit the cellular growth of tumor cells **SK-OV-3** and they have less effects on **HdFn** normal cell line (table 6)

The results shown that the (curcumin) have high Cytotoxicity effect on **SK-OV-3** cell line by using different concentration for (curcumin) (400,200,100,50,25µg/ml) , the Viability of **HdFn** cells of curcumin was (79.2,84.1,89.8,93.4 ,94.25) As in a table (3-1) ,while the Viability of **SK-OV-3** cells of curcumin was (39.50,51.65,62.77,72.02,87.11) respectively, as in a table (6) :

Table (6): Comparison study between the cytotoxic effect of curcumin on HdFn and SK-OV-3 cell lines

Concentration µg mL ⁻¹	Mean viability (%) ± SD	
	HdFn	SK-OV-3
400	79.20±1.57	39.50±4.003
200	84.14±2.23	51.65±1.44
100	89.89±2.18	62.77±4.29

50	93.40±0.53	72.02±0.69
25	94.25±1.14	87.11±2.77

In addition, the results showed significant differences $P \leq 0.0001$ when calculating the **IC₅₀** for curcumin (170.2,149.4) for HdFn ,SK-OV-3 respectively, as in Figure (10):

Figure (10) Dose - dependent cytotoxic effect of Curcumin on SK-OV-3 and HdFn

3.2 B Cytotoxic effect of [H8] on Ovarian cancer and healthy cell lines (MTT assay):

When investigating the [H8] compound associated with curcumin it showed very high activity against SK-OV-3 cells. The Viability HdFn cells rate for [H8] it was (73.4,85.2,92.5,94.2,95.0) , while the Viability of SK-OV-3 cells of [H8] was (32.90,39.77,42.90, 52. 006,65.47) respectively, by using different concentration for [H8] (25,50,100,200,400 µg/ml) as in a table (7)

Table (7): Comparison study between the cytotoxic effect of [H8], on HdFn and SK-OV-3 cell lines

Concentration µg mL ⁻¹	Mean viability (%) ± SD	
	HdFn	SK-OV-3
400	73.41±1.57	32.90±1.34
200	85.26±0.99	39.77±1.44
100	92.51±1.52	42.90±2.41
50	94.25±0.37	52.006±5.100
25	95.023±0.92	65.47±0.86

[H8] reduced cell viability in a dose-dependent manner with a calculating **IC₅₀** (81.30µg/ml) of **SK-OV-3**, while normal cell **HdFn** (277.9µg/ml). as in Figure (11):

Figure (11) Dose - dependent cytotoxic effect of [H8] on SK-OV-3 and HdFn

3.2 C Effect of Curcumin – Ether – 1,3,4 Oxadiazol on caspases 8 and caspases 9 Activity

The [H8] complicated, which exhibits the highest level of anticancer activity according to [MTT assay] results, was selected to assess caspases 8 and 9, which are thought to be inducers of apoptosis activity. This is because both caspase pathways intrinsic and extrinsic catalyze the proteolytic activation of the caspase cascade, which results in cell destruction. SK-OV-3 cells were used in this experiment to confirm whether or not the caspase pathway is involved in the apoptosis caused by the [H8] Compound.

The results was shown in figure (12) and table (8) that illustrated the caspase -8 activities in SK-OV-3 cell line at both concentrations (100 & 200) $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and compared to DMSO as control. casepase 8 revealed that there significance increases of SK-OV-3 in 200 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of [H8] (9.28%) , while there was non-significant effect on cells in 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of [H8] Where the percentage was 5.83% . as in table (8) and figure (12) .

Table (8) Effect of[H8] on caspase 8 activity at (100 and 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Multiple Comparison of Caspase 8 Activity SK-OV-3 Cells BetweenH8 and Untreated Cells			
Treatments($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Mean Activity \pm SD	Sig.	p value
DMSO	14525.33 \pm 1113.273	-----	-----
100	15438 \pm 1532.228	ns	<0.05
200	24432.67 \pm 1567.027	***	<0.05

NS: Non-significant, **: $p \leq 0.01$, SD: Standard Deviation

Figure (12): Mean , SD caspase 8 activity in SK-OV-3 cells. Activity measured in luminescence against [H8] concentrations (100 , 200 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and Negative control (doxorubicine 1 mM). treatments were compared with control cells. NS: Non- Significant, **: $p \leq 0.05$, SD: Standard Deviation, ($n = 3$)

while casepase9 revealed that there significance increases of SK-OV-3 in 100 and 200 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of [H10] (38.3% , 25.8%) respectively , and compared DMSO as control while there was non-significant effect on cells in 50,25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of [H8] as a shown in table (9) and figure (13)

Table (9) Effect of[H8] on caspase 9 activity at (100 and 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Multiple Comparison of Caspase 9 Activity SK-OV-3 Cells BetweenH8 and Untreated Cells			
Treatments($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Mean Activity \pm SD	Sig.	p value
DMSO	15289 \pm 2006.807	-----	-----
100	39894.67 \pm 4036.303	***	<0.05
200	59087 \pm 3108.904	****	<0.05

Figure (13): Mean , SD caspase 9 activity in SK-OV-3 cells. Activity measured in luminescence against [H8] concentrations (100 , 200 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and Negative control (doxorubicine 1 mM). treatments were compared with control cells. NS: Non-Significant, **: $p \leq 0.05$, SD: Standard Deviation, ($n = 3$).

Caspase-8, which comprises both intrinsic and extrinsic pathways, and caspase-9, which mainly consists of intrinsic pathways that initiate upon the death ligand's interaction with the receptor of the surface death, are the primary initiator caspases. The proapoptotic BCL-2 family members facilitate the transportation of cytochrome c into the cytosol and interact with Apaf-1 and pro-caspase 9 to form a heptameric complex (apoptosome) in the presence of ATP. The caspase-8 activates apoptosis by activating the executioner caspases or by cleaving Bid to form the truncated Bid (tBid) that affects the releases of cytochrome c from the mitochondria⁽²⁹⁾.

The cell contain an enzymes called cysteine proteases which have different functions, and these caspases are receiving apoptosis signals so the initiator caspases are activated which led to activate the executioner caspases. As a result of this process, the Ca^{+2} ion concentration are increase in the intracellular, regulate the activation of DNA binding transcription factor and ROS are produced. After that, the cytochrome C that found in mitochondrial membrane are released and the activation of caspase-8 & 9 (initiator caspase) are start and the apoptosis are induced⁽³⁰⁾

From data obtained from (MTT, Caspases 8,9) Assays , the following observation can be drawn .

1. (MTT, Caspases 8,9) Assays are used in this research to measure cellular metabolic activity as an indicator and cytotoxicity .
2. Curcumin , [H8] compound reduced the viability of **SK-OV-3** cell line , the cell viability decreased with the increase in the applied concentration Curcumin , [H8] and the higher decrease was detected at the highest concentration.
3. Cytotoxicity test result , showed that Curcumin , [H8] has concentration dependent anti proliferative effect on **SK-OV-3** cell ,

IC50 for curcumin = 149.4 μ g/ml

IC50 for [H8] = 81.30 μ g/ml

4. Curcumin , [H8] compound are significantly reduced the viability of SK-OV-3 cell , the percentage of dead of early apoptotic and late apoptotic cell were detected to be :-

Curcumin (21%, 61%) at 400 μ g/ml on HdFn , SK-OV-3 cell respectively.

(16%, 49%) at 200 μ g/ml on HdFn , SK-OV-3 cell respectively

[H8] (27%, 69%) at 400 μ g/ml on HdFn , SK-OV-3 cell respectively

(15%,61%) at 200 μ g/ml on HdFn , SK-OV-3 cell respectively

5. curcumin⁽³¹⁾efficiently promotes apoptosis in a range of cell lines and this result is compatible with result obtained which indicated that curcumin had a strong anti-proliferative activity against leukemia cell by causing DNA damage in cancer cells , which in tumor triggered apoptosis in those cell .
6. (curcumin- 1,3,4 – Oxadiazole) hybrid compound [H8] showed higher cytotoxic activity on Ovarian cancer cell compound with curcumin, the introducing 1,3,4-oxadiazole on the structure at curcumin improve anti-cancer activity. They more effectively inhibit cancer cell proliferation ,induced apoptosis , and interfere with cell cycle regulation .
7. The combination of 1,3,4 – oxadiazole ring system with curcumin lead to increase the stability of curcumin in body human , increasing bioavailability , an also the presence of such ring help to improve the absorption of curcumin in the gastrointestinal tract , and enhancing the properties of curcumin such as preventing the proliferation of cancer cells and stimulating apoptosis .
8. The main mechanism of action by which curcumin and derivative [H8] exhibits anti- ovarian cancer activity could be explained by:-
 - 1) Inducing apoptosis .
 - 2) Inhibiting the proliferation .
 - 3) Invasion of tumors by suppressing various cellular suppressing .

9. In conclusion, the present study has shown that curcumin and [H8] compound suppressed the growth of (SK-OV-3).

3.3 molecular docking study of curcumin, 1,3,4-oxadiazole, hybrid (curcumin-1,3,4-oxadiazole) compounds (cur.H4,H8) with Bcl-2 and Bcl XL proteins.

The docking⁽³²⁾ results were ranked according to the binding affinity of select compound-protein complex as presented in Table (10):

Table (10): Docking scores Kcal/mole and interactions of compounds (curcumin, H4, H8,) with BCL-2 and BCL-x1 proteins

Protein	Ligand	Binding affinity (kcal/mol)	Hydrogen bonding	Hydrophobic interaction	Electrostatic interaction
BCL-2	[H4]	-6.0	PHE63	ALA59 ALA108 ARG105 ALA108	—
	curcumin	-7.9	—	PHE63 PHE63 PHE63 PHE112	—
	[H8]	-9.2	TYR67	ALA59 PHE63 PHE71	ASP62 ASP62
BCL-x1	[H4]	-6.8	ARG139	ALA104 PHE97 PHE105 ARG139	
	curcumin	-8.8	ARG139	ALA104 ALA104 ALA104 ALA104 TYR101 PHE105 PHE105 PHE105	ARG139
	[H8]	-11.9	ARG139 ARG132 ASP133 TRY101	ALA104 LEU130 ALA104 ALA142 PHE97 TYR101 PHE105 PHE97 PHE105	ARG139 ARG139

And from the data obtained from table (3-7) the following observation results can be drawn:-

3.3 A- Docked with B-cell lymphoma 2 protein

1. The docked results showed that compound [H8] has the highest binding affinities of -9.2 kcal/mol. In contrast, compound [H4] showed the lowest binding affinity of -6.0 kcal/mol compared with curcumin.

- Hydrogen bonds were observed in the (BCL-2–select compound) complex for compounds [H4,H8] but not with curcumin of two residues, that is PHE-63 and Tyr67 (Table 10).
- PHE63, TYR161, ALA59, ARG105, ALA108, PHE112, MET174, ASP62, TYR161 were found near 1,3,4-oxadiazole and curcumin moieties.

3.3 B- Docked with B-cell lymphoma-extra-large protein

- Analyses of the docked select compound with Bcl-x1 protein suggested that all select compounds have better interaction with BCL-x1 protein that with BCL-2
- The docked results showed that compound [H8] has the highest binding affinities of -11.3 kcal/mol. In contrast, compound [H4] showed the lowest binding affinity of -6.8 kcal/mol compared with curcumin .
- Hydrogen bonds were observed in the (BCL-x1 –select compound) complex for all select compounds
- Based on the binding interactions, one critical residue (ARG139) of Bcl-x1 protein interacted with all compounds either via hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic or electrostatic interactions.
- ALA104, PHE97, PHE105, ARG139, TYR101, PHE105, LUE130, ALA142, ASP133 were found near 1,3,4-oxadiazole and curcumin moieties .

The docking results (with Bcl-2 and BCL-X1) showed exact compatibility with in vitro cytotoxicity for compound [H8] this result indicated that the introducing of 1,3,4-oxadiazole enhance the biological activity of curcumin because this ring added more binding interactions, added more stability and more affinity due to its 1,3,4-oxadiazole constitution which contains (two nitrogen and one oxygen atoms, two imine bonds) which considers as electron donors leading to increase binding interactions of compound [H8] with BCL-2 and BCL-x1 proteins, Fig (14)-fig(19) shows docking models and interaction between compounds (curcumin, [H4],[H8]).

Figure (14): 3D and 2D docking models and interaction between compound [H4] and the enzyme BCL-2

Figure (15): 3D and 2D docking models and interaction between curcumin and the enzyme BCL-2

Figure (16): 3D and 2D docking models and interaction between [H8] compound and the enzyme BCL-2

Figure (17): 3D and 2D docking models and interaction between [H4] compound and the enzyme BCL-x1

Figure (18): 3D and 2D docking models and interaction between curcumin and the enzyme BCL-x1

Figure (19): 3D and 2D docking models and interaction between [H8] and the enzyme BCL-x1

4. Conclusions:

1. four of novel hybrid (curcumin – 1,3,4- oxadiazole) compounds have been successfully prepared using experimental methods offer an easy experimental work up with good product yield .
2. Combination of spectral data obtained (FT-IR, 1H-NMR,Mass spectroscopy) in addition to physical properties gives a good evidence for successful hybridization of curcumin with 1,3,4-oxadiazole through ether these modification lead to increasing rigidity and thermal stability of hybrid molecules due increasing aromatic characters .
3. The combination results of cytotoxic activity (MTT, Caspases 8,9 assay) of two (SK-OV-3 and HdFn) cell line indicated that the more active compounds against(SK-OV-3) cell line were in the following order: Compound [H8] > curcumin

4. From the above result it was demonstrated that the cytotoxic activity of curcumin could be increased by incorporating with 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring system .
5. The molecular docking simulation results indicated that combination of curcumin with 1,3,4-oxadiazole improve the results of binding score through the increasing of H-bonds, vander-walls, and hydrophobic interactions which are responsible for forming stable compound of the hybrid molecule ligand with receptor proteins, and the result obtained showed that compound [H8] have the highest binding affinity (-9.2 and -11.9) with Bcl-2 and Bcl-Xl respectively .
6. These conclusion make compound [H8] an interesting compound for further research to better understand the anti-cancer mechanism.
7. the combination of the docking studies and cytotoxic evaluation of curcumin and [H8] showed that these compounds lower SK-OV-3 cell viability , increases pro apoptotic proteins, and decreases Bcl-2 level therapy inhibiting SK-OV-3 tumor growth , these finding engorge us to development of anew synthetic strategy for cancer treatment .

References

1. S. A. Farghaly, *Advances in diagnosis and management of ovarian cancer*: Springer, 2013.
2. R. E. Bristow, B. Y. Karlan, and D. S. Chi, *Surgery for ovarian cancer: principles and practice*: CRC Press, 2010.
3. Cancer Annual Report [database on the Internet]. *Iraqi Ministry of Health/Iraqi Cancer Board*. 2022. [cited 1/7/2021]. Available from: <https://moh.gov.iq/upload/upfile/ar/106def1.pdf>.
4. J. Sharifi-Rad, Y.E. Rayess, A.A. Rizk, C. Sadaka, R. Zgheib, W. Zam, N. Martins, Turmeric and its major compound curcumin on health: bioactive effects and safety profiles for food, pharmaceutical, biotechnological and medicinal applications, *Front. Pharmacol.* 11 (2020) 1021.
5. H. Tang, C.J. Murphy, B. Zhang, Y. Shen, M. Sui, E.A. Van Kirk, W.J. Murdoch, Amphiphilic curcumin conjugate-forming nanoparticles as anticancer prodrug and drug carriers: in vitro and in vivo effects, *Nanomedicine* 5 (6) (2010) 855–865.
6. N. Dhillon, B.B. Aggarwal, R.A. Newman, R.A. Wolff, A.B. Kunnumakkara, J.L. Abbruzzese, R. Kurzrock, Phase II trial of curcumin in patients with advanced pancreatic cancer, *Clin. Cancer Res.* 14 (14) (2008) 4491–4499.
7. B. Aggarwal, A. Kumar , A.C. Bharti . *Anticancer Res.* **2003**, *23*, 363-398.
8. F.H. Sarkar , Y. Li , Z. Wang .S. Padhye . *Curr. Pharm. Des.* **2010**, *16*, 1801-1812.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/138161210791208956>
9. M.A.Tomeh . R. Hadianamrei. X. Zhao. A Review of Curcumin and Its Derivatives as Anticancer Agents. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2019**, *20*, 1033. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
10. M.H. Teiten, M.Dicato, M. Diederich, M. Hybrid Curcumin Compounds: A New Strategy for Cancer Treatment. *Molecules* **2014**, *19*, 20839–20863. [CrossRef]
11. Q. Zhang, Y. Zhong, L-N.Yan, X. Sun, T. Gong, Z-R. Zhang. Synthesis and preliminary evaluation of curcumin analogues as cytotoxic agents. *Bioorganic Med. Chem. Lett.* **2011**, *21*, 1010–1014. [CrossRef]
12. S. Prasad, A.K. Tyagi, B.B. Aggarwal, Recent developments in delivery, bioavailability, absorption and metabolism of curcumin: the golden pigment from golden spice, *Cancer. Res. Treat.: Off. J. Korean Cancer Assoc.* 46 (1) (2014) 2.
13. P. Anand, A.B. Kunnumakkara, R.A. Newman, B.B. Aggarwal, Bioavailability of curcumin: problems and promises, *Mol. Pharm.* 4 (6) (2007) 807–818.
14. M. Dei Cas, R. Ghidoni, Dietary curcumin: correlation between bioavailability and health potential, *Nutrients* 11 (9) (2019) 2147.

15. W. Liu, Y. Zhai, X. Heng, F.Y. Che, W. Chen, D. Sun, G. Zhai, Oral bioavailability of curcumin: problems and advancements, *J. Drug Target.* 24 (8) (2016) 694–702
16. P. Pitasse-Santos, V. Sueth-Santiago, M.E.F. Lima, 1,2,4- and 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles As Scaffolds in the Development of Antiparasitic Agents, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.* 29 (2018) 435–456. <https://doi.org/10.21577/0103-5053.20170208>.
17. B.M. Ramana, M.G. Rao, M. Krishna Murthy, R. Varala, H. Babu Bollikolla, C.B. Ramana M, M.G. Rao, M. Murthy, H. Babu Bollikolla, Strategies to Synthesis of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Derivatives and Their Biological Activities: A Mini Review, *J. Chem. Rev.* 4 (2022) 255–271. <https://doi.org/10.22034/JCR.2022.341351.1170>.
18. S. Bajaj, P.P. Roy, J. Singh, 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles as Telomerase Inhibitor: Potential Anticancer Agents, *Anticancer. Agents Med. Chem.* 17 (2017) 1869–1883. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1871521409666170425092906>
19. S. Zhang, Y. Luo, L.Q. He, Z.J. Liu, A.Q. Jiang, Y.H. Yang, H.L. Zhu, Synthesis, biological evaluation, and molecular docking studies of novel 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives possessing benzotriazole moiety as FAK inhibitors with anticancer activity, *Bioorganic Med. Chem.* 21 (2013) 3723–3729. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2013.04.043>.
20. Q.R. Du, D.D. Li, Y.Z. Pi, J.R. Li, J. Sun, F. Fang, W.Q. Zhong, H. Bin Gong, H.L. Zhu, Novel 1,3,4-oxadiazole thioether derivatives targeting thymidylate synthase as dual anticancer/antimicrobial agents, *Bioorganic Med. Chem.* 21 (2013) 2286–2297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2013.02.008>.
21. Y. Ono, M. Ninomiya, D. Kaneko, A.D. Sonawane, T. Udagawa, K. Tanaka, A. Nishina, M. Koketsu, Design and synthesis of quinoxaline-1,3,4-oxadiazole hybrid derivatives as potent inhibitors of the anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 protein, *Bioorg. Chem.* 104 (2020) 104245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2020.104245>.
22. C.D. Mohan, N.C. Anilkumar, S. Rangappa, M.K. Shanmugam, S. Mishra, A. Chinnathambi, S.A. Alharbi, A. Bhattacharjee, G. Sethi, A.P. Kumar, Basappa, K.S. Rangappa, Novel 1,3,4-oxadiazole induces anticancer activity by targeting NF- κ B in hepatocellular carcinoma cells, *Front. Oncol.* 8 (2018) 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2018.00042>.
23. M.J. Ahsan, A. Choupra, R.K. Sharma, S.S. Jadav, P. Padmaja, M.Z. Hassan, A.B.S. Al-Tamimi, M.H. Geesi, M.A. Bakht, Rationale Design, Synthesis, Cytotoxicity Evaluation, and Molecular Docking Studies of 1,3,4-oxadiazole Analogues, *Anticancer. Agents Med. Chem.* 18 (2017) 121–138. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1871520617666170419124702>.
24. K. Biernacki, et al., Novel 1, 2, 4-oxadiazole derivatives in drug discovery. *Pharmaceuticals*, 2020. **13**(6): p. 111.
25. P. Agu, et al., Molecular docking as a tool for the discovery of molecular targets of nutraceuticals in diseases management. *Scientific Reports*, 2023. **13**(1): p. 13398.
26. Y. K. Alasadi, F. H. Jumaa, A.H. Dalaf, S. M. Shawkat, M. G. Mukhlif. Synthesis, Characterization, and Molecular Docking of New Tetrazole Derivatives as Promising Anticancer Agents. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 13(3) (2022) 513-522.
27. S. Agarwal, R. Mehrotra, An Overview of Molecular Simulation, *JSM Chem.* 4 (2016) 1024–1028. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Shweta-Agarwal-7/publication/303897563_Mini_Review_An_overview_of_Molecular_Docking/links/575b9fb108aed884620da00a/Mini-Review-An-overview-of-Molecular-Docking.pdf.
28. R. Bristow and D. Armstrong, *Early Diagnosis and Treatment of Cancer Series: Ovarian Cancer E-Book: Elsevier Health Sciences*, 2015.

29. Y. Tian , Y. Liu , S. Tian , S. Ge , Y. Wu , B. Zhang . Antitumor activity of ginsenoside Rd in gastric cancer via up-regulation of Caspase-3 and Caspase-9, *Pharmazie*, 2020, Vol. 75, P: 147-150.
30. WS. Kim, , KS. Lee, JH. Kim, C. Kim, G. Lee, J. Choe, M. H. Won, TH. Kim, D. Jeoung, H. Lee, JY.Kim, M. Jeong, KS. Ha, Y.Kwon, and K. Misun. The caspase-8/Bid/cytochrome C axis links signals from death receptors to mitochondrial reactive oxygen species production. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*. 112(2017)..
31. AK. Ghosh, NE. Kay, CR. Secreto, and TD. Shanafelt, . Curcumin inhibits prosurvival pathways in chronic lymphocytic leukemia B cells and may overcome their stromal protection in combination with EGCG. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 15. (2009).
32. O. Trott , AJ. Olson . Autodock Vina: improving the speed and accuracy of docking with a new scoring function, efficient optimization, and multithreading. *J Comput Chem*. 2010;31:455–61. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar].